

80%), m.p. 370°; $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 1 620 (C=N), 1 680 (C=O), 1 530–1 494 (N–C=S) and 3 290–3 110 cm^{-1} (NH).

Since the compounds were insoluble in most of the deuterated solvents and soluble in hot D_2O with decomposition, the nmr spectra could not be

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA AND ACTIVITIES OF N-ARYL-FORMAMIDINO-N'-SUBSTITUTED-THIOSEMICARBAZONES

Compd. no.	Mol. formula	M p °C	Yield %	Relative activity (for thiouracil activity=1 000)
4a	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_6\text{OSCl}$	310	80	0.812
4b	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{OSCl}$	315	78	0.755
4d	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{OSCl}$	323	75	0.773
4f	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_6\text{OSCl}_2$	317	75	1.031
4g	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_6\text{OSCl}_2$	287	70	1.039
4h	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{SCl}$	320	74	0.818
4j	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{SCl}$	312	81	0.823
4k	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{SCl}$	315	80	0.907
4l	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{SCl}$	318	75	0.958
5a	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{OSCl}$	292	72	0.704
5b	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_6\text{OSCl}$	295	70	0.674
5d	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_6\text{OSCl}$	290	69	0.669
5h	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{SCl}$	296	72	0.846
5j	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{SCl}$	280	75	0.853
6a	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{SCl}$	170	75	0.823
6b	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{SCl}$	185	66	0.780
6c	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{SCl}$	192	72	0.812
6d	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{SCl}$	190	70	0.820
6e	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_6\text{SCl}_2$	183	65	1.050
6g	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_6\text{SCl}_2$	180	68	1.073
6h	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{OSCl}$	175	60	0.832
6i	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{OSCl}$	173	67	0.818
6j	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{OSCl}$	179	65	0.826
7a	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_6\text{SCl}$	230	60	0.853
7b	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{SCl}$	225	62	0.814
7c	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{SCl}$	223	65	0.818
7d	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{SCl}$	220	60	0.820
7f	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{SCl}_2$	222	69	1.067
7g	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{SCl}_2$	227	65	1.077
7h	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{OSCl}$	210	55	0.822
7j	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{OSCl}$	217	68	0.826
7k	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{OSCl}$	220	70	0.937
8a	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{SCl}$	215	70	0.782
8b	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{SCl}$	185	65	0.757
8d	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{SCl}$	230	62	0.770
8f	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{SCl}_2$	225	55	1.078
8g	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{SCl}_2$	226	62	1.094
8h	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{SCl}$	215	67	0.833
8j	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{SCl}$	220	60	0.844

recorded. On boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid, substituted-thiosemicarbazone and phenylurea were obtained which were identified through undepressed m.m.p. with authentic samples.

The other analogues of 4 and 5 were prepared following a similar procedure. Compounds 6–8 were prepared similarly, except that DMSO was replaced by acetone and the reaction was carried out by cooling in ice-salt mixture in case of 6 and 7 and only in ice in case of 8.

Compounds 4–8 were evaluated¹¹ for their antithyroid activity. All compounds (dissolved in saline for i.p. injection) were assayed at concentrations equimolar to 0.5 mg of thiouracil (3.9 μmol), used as standard, and the biological effects summarised in Table 1. The results indicate that the compounds having chlorine in aryl nucleus exhibit maximum activity; the *p*-chloro derivatives are marginally more potent.

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